

THE IMPORTANCE AND VIABILITY OF FOSS IN VIDEOGAME PRODUCTION

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Abstract

The free culture and FOSS (Free Open Source Software) movements aren't new concepts, proof of that is the increasing number of projects following this kind of philosophy. However common users tend to avoid FOSS instead of contributing to the betterment of such alternatives to proprietary solutions. Although people understand philosophy behind such concepts, they tend to avoid using FOSS in fear of it not meeting their needs.

A project aiming to prove that free alternatives such as FOSS are a worthy alternative was born. A videogame was made from the ground up using only FOSS and Freeware solutions, along with free assets made available to the community for free, filling the gaps where the team had no expert to solve (such as sound effects). During the development of this project, several aspects of the software being used were analyzed in order to better discern the advantages and disadvantages of using these free alternatives.

Keywords: Free Software, Open Source, Free Culture, Game Design, Indie Videogame.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Presentation

The evolution of technology and the constant accessibility to information has undoubtedly brought infinite opportunities of growth to all fields of work and research. The digital world has changed Irreversibly the way we live and consequently how we see and interact with the world.

In creative fields of work, the digital medium presents itself as a powerful tool in an artists life. There is an endless range of information and tools for creating and editing digital content. Although there are already many powerful tools widely known, many of them have some features that may restrict or limit the user in some ways. Closed source and proprietary Software can some times be expensive with few personalizable features and unknown future direction.

The limited nature of closed propriety software is a problem for us, we believe that every one should have the opportunity and tools to create something out of nothing without being restricted be a label. This project sought out to find and implement Free and Open alternative solutions for the digital creative process and through them prove the viability and benefits of FOSS (Free and Open Source Software) and Freeware. This project was developed in an academic context, for a masters degree in Illustration and Animation (MIA) at the Polytechnic Institute of Cavado and Ave in Portugal. This project was made possible thanks to the collaboration of a proqramer with the artist responsible for this it.

We decided to create a videogame using only these concepts to prove their feasibility and contribute to the dissemination of FOSS as a relevant and viable framework for a videogame production pipeline. Our project aims to help proving that FOSS is a worthy alternative. The videogame was developed using only software freely available, mainly FOSS, along with free assets. During the development of the videogame prototype some tools were created and contributions were made to existing FOSS projects in order to solve emerging problems.

1.2 Relevance and objectivity

Nowadays most common digital users employ proprietary software and some don't even know what that means. This option depends on a negotiation, not always conscious, between the features provides by these technologies and the terms and conditions defined by the companies responsible

for developing proprietary software.

There are many examples that legitimize the relevance of this problem. The simple act of banning the possibility of making a copy of the legally purchased software, for backup or resale are just two examples of common constraints. The software when purchased does not belong to it's user, instead, it is property of the company responsible for it's development and distribution. For the user this means giving up control over their creation tools, their means of creation are subject to constraints that are external to the user.

According to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (United Nations, 1948, Article 27), all individuals have "the right to participate freely in cultural life community, to enjoy the arts and to be part of the scientific advancement and its benefits ". However, The same document also establishes the "right to protect the moral and material interests resulting from any scientific, literary or artistic production."

This project is very focused on our rights as users and as a creators. In one hand we sought out to find the tools technically capable and accessible that make the creative process possible. And on the other end, we intend to give prominence to the importance of a more share alike attitude, by doing it ourselves. We are sharing and giving our contribute to the digital community, with what we created using open and free alternatives. This way, we provide assets and information to all those like us, interested in creating digital content, in this case a videogame.

"Free art and a free culture, is of vital Importance for a free society" (Myers, 2008, p. 311).

Choosing to use open and free Software is not just an option of economical interest, but much more, it's a matter of freedom.

"To use free software is to make a political and ethical choice asserting the right to learn, and share what we learn with others. Free software has become the foundation of a learning society where we share our knowledge in a way that others can build upon and enjoy" (FSF, Jonh Sullivan).

We feel the need of proving the viability of free and open software as an important resource, mainly due to the stigma created around this concept. Due to the vast acceptability and non profitable interest (in many cases) behind the open community of developers, there is a vast list of examples of software that are insufficient, incomplete and abandoned. Lost within thees are powerful and well structured digital tools. Capable of preforming the tasks presented. The videogame is a very complex and phased product, it depends on a vast range of assets to preform as wanted. We saw this as an opportunity to explore different types of open and free software, in a way to compose a solid group of open digital alternatives thought tried out for videogame production.

1.3 F/LOSS and Free Culture

The expressions FOSS (Free and Open Source Software) and FLOSS (Free / Libre and Open Source Software) are commonly used to describe the aggregation two movements known as Free Software and Open Source Software. Although they are two distinct movements, they share some of the same principals.

The term Free Software was first used By Richard Stallman, a hacker from MIT (Massachusetts Institute of Technology) in 1983 upon announcement of the GNU project, an operating system that is developed and distributed without the constraints imposed by proprietary nature software. In 1985, Richard Stallman founded the Free Software Foundation (FSF), a non-profitable organization that promotes the freedom of sharing, modifying and distributing software without restriction. For the FSF (FSF, 2013) free software represents any software distributed with a license that meets the following four "freedoms":

- ^ The freedom to run the program for any purpose (freedom 0);
- ^ The freedom to study the program's functionality and adapt it to your needs, impling access to the source code (Freedom 1);
- ^ The freedom to redistribute copies so as to help the neighbor (freedom 2);
- ^ The freedom to distribute copies (including source code) of modified versions giving others the opportunity to benefit from these (Freedom 3).

It's important to clarify the possible misunderstanding of the term "free" used to describe free software. "Free" in free software refers to the freedom of sharing, creating and distributing software, it's a matter

of freedom and not price. To better understand the concept, you should think of "free " as in "free speech" and not as in " free beer".

The term Open Source was born alongside the emergence of the Open Source initiative in 1998. An organization founded by Bruce Perens and Eric Raymond in order to promote a new approach to software and encourage a collective collaboration on building more and better software. The founders of this movement recognize the inspiration in various ideals introduced by the FSF, although It has a more practical vision than a more ethical approach like the free software moment.

“For the Open Source movement, the issue of whether software should be open source is a practical question, not an ethical one.” (Stallman, 2010, p. 57).

In general both moments are seen as an alternative to proprietary software, and tend to grow within the digital community. Currently we are witnessing an increasing number of companies who adopt FOSS as a development and distribution tool for its software: Google (Android, YouTube), Facebook, MBNet, Walt Disney (Ptex) Lucasfilm (OpenEXR), Sony Pictures Imageworks (Open Shading Language), DreamWorks Animation (OpenVDB), among others.

There are more examples of important movements that share the same concerns as the Foss community and apply their work on other forms beyond Software. Free Culture is a social moment concerned with the restrictions imposed by the Copyright. The Free Software, Open Source Software and Free Culture share their concern about the power and control of entities over proprietary software and cultural content. The Free Software and Open Source are focused on developing tools like software, while the Free Culture extends it's work to artistic and cultural production. In order to apply a sharing attitude, the Free Culture moves along alternative organizations to the purest concept of "All rights reserved". Through the use of tools such as Creative Commons (CC) and Copyleft licenses, we can use the legal basis of copyright to create greater flexibility when licensing our own artistic and cultural creations, giving the author back the power of decision on how they would like to make available their creations.

2 THE PROTOTYPE

2.1 Concept

It is important to anticipate and realize the potential fragility of some of Free and Open Source software. Due to its nature, there are some poorly built and consequently abandoned software, which has made an impact on the overall repudiation FOSS. To contradict this theory we feel the need to prove the viability of these products and if necessary, create bridges between software so to complete them and create a working platform for professional and commercial production.

We don't intend in any way to degrade or devalue propriety software, this project only serves as a reference to other alternatives based on a philosophy of freedom of sharing. We intend on bringing more users to get to know what Free and Open software has to give, and in return help build more great resources.

Along with our motivation to create something using only FOSS, we thought that creating a Videogame and presenting it in a academic environment was the best alternative This project was thought out and created for the purpose of the conclusion of a masters degree on Illustration and animation. We where inspired to create something that would have illustration as a core asset. Therefor we defined the videogame has being 2D and of a platform gameplay, that way we could take more advantage of the power of the illustrations.

Alongside this project Rolling Pixels was created, a group consisting of only two members; Natacha Lourosa aka NatiiWorks the digital artist and Michael Dias he programmer. The group was formed with the initiative to create indie videogames, using this prototype has a booster project.

2.2 Used Resources

The software is one of the parts of this project that mos attention deserve. In a way to better illustrate the resources used during this project, we created a list where we present all software used.

Software used for the purpose of game design:

- ^ MyPaint - MyPaint is an Open Source tool built for digital drawing and painting. It's available for Windows and GNU / Linux systems. It has a simple and minimal interface designed with the

intention of causing less distractions to the user. Mypaint Contains various brushes that simulate traditional artistic techniques, with the possibility of creating and customizing brushes. For this project, this tool was used in Arch Linux and Windows 7 operating systems throughout the drafting process. Based on our experience, we find that Mypaint is a powerful tool for digital drawing and painting.

- ^ Krita – Krita is an Open Source and Free software tool, used for digital drawing, painting and image edition. It has much more features for image editing than Mypaint, and is better built for creating complex illustrations. It was included in the creation process for this project due to a lack of features in Mypaint. This software is very complete and ideal for more detailed work. Krita is more stable when used in the KDE desktop environment for GNU / Linux, otherwise it can be a very unstable tool.
- ^ Gimp – Gimp is a multi-platform Software for image editing, specially prepared for tasks such as retouching and image composition. There are also different versions specially designed for digital painting and simple animation. this tool was used on all images created for this prototype, which were cut, resized, exported and corrected the color level. Gimp is one of the best Open Source software tools built for digital image editing.
- ^ Blender – Blender is an Open Source 3D modeling Software used in this project mainly as a level editor. Blender is a very stable and powerful tool for 3D modeling and animation, however we did feel some witnesses when using Blender as a game editor. Compared to the other tools used, Blender is the better documented Software with better technical support. Overall Blender fulfilled our needs, but we do feel it has great potential for becoming a better tool for Videogame editing.
- ^ Sprite Sheet Packer - An Open Source software for automated creation of atlas. this software though small and simple when it comes to functionality, it was an important tool for accelerating the process of videogame production, this is due the number of images used. Along with the atlas, this software creates automatically a small text file with all coordinates of different images organized in the atlas.
- ^ Bulk Rename Utility - Free software used to rename files simultaneously to prevent the repetition of file names.
- ^ Audacity – A Free and Open Source audio editor. this program was used to edit the sound tracks used in the level. It is a software simple issue that corresponded to the needs editing, cutting and processing of sound bands used.

Software used for programing and creating the videogames logic.

- ^ QtCreator - IDE (integrated development environment) for programming in C + +. It's Open Source and works on Windows, GNU / Linux, FreeBSD and Mac OS.
- ^ MonoDevelop - Open Source IDE for multi-programming in C # and other programming languages based on. NET.
- ^ CMake - Open Source and cross-platform digital tool for maganing and compiling Software.
- ^ Microsoft Visual Studio Express - IDE for programming in C + + (and other languages not used in this project). It has a free version for Windows.

All the other resources like sound and textures, were downloaded from free online libraries, with none or little restriction of use.

2.3 Contribution

One of the main goals of this project involves the public distribution of the prototype. Along with the prototype we want to make available some of the content used for it's creation, like game art and software. We want this to happen so that others like ourselves will be more equipped with tools for creating videogames freely. Besides some of our assets, we also intend on making available some plug-ins specially created for the purpose of producing this game.

We believe that our main contribution is based on the fact that we have proven possible and feasible the creation of a complex product, like a videogame, using only FOSS, we hope to encourage and inform others throwout this experience.

Based on our experience we present some of the advantages and disadvantages that we felt when using FOSS.

2.3.1 Advantages

- ^ Free access to software.
 - o The software used during the development of this project was well documented and mature. The best example of this is Blender, mostly used as a level editor.
- ^ Ability to change the source code in order to customize it to better adjust to the users' need, or fix a bug that's stopping your progress.
 - o We took advantage of this by optimizing the rendering engine (Ogre3D) for 2D rendering. We were also able to improve antialiasing of MyPaint brushes.
- ^ Better communication with software authors.
 - o It's usually easier to engage in conversations with the software writers directly. This allows the community to help shape the software more directly.

2.3.2 Disadvantages

- ^ Resource fragmentation. Due to a mix of specific personal needs and different opinions, people tend to fork (create derived works) the original software and go in a different direction instead of contributing directly to the original work.
- ^ Lack of monetary investment may result in lower quality software because developers may lack the time for proper investigation of certain aspects such as interface design and others.
- ^ Software instability - Due to the free (as in freedom) nature of FOSS as well as lack of resources, some software doesn't have Quality Assurance and some features may not work properly or even cause data loss in the event of a software crash.
- ^ No tech support - There are a few applications that do offer tech support (sometimes paid), however the majority of FOSS does not.

3 CONCLUSION

Working only with FOSS tools on such a complex product has proven how rich and powerful some Free and Open Source Software examples are, all available and well documented with great potential. There were obviously some weaknesses revealed during this process, but in most of the times, thanks to access to the source code, most bugs and problems were fixed. We must stress that without Free and open resources, it would have been nearly impossible to have created our prototype. There are many indie developers just like us with the inability to financially invest in their projects. This shouldn't be a world driven by money and power but instead by great ideas, and FOSS is a great solid work platform to accomplish such ideas.

We had already previous experience with some of the software used, that helped us better organize all the process and better combine the work done on other software. We did feel the lack of a better software for level editing, although we had positive results using Blender, we feel the need of more investment towards that area.

Throughout this experience we had the pleasure to witness what's more comforting about working in community, the sense of help and collaboration is well present within the FOSS community. We had direct conversations with people responsible for the development of some of the software, whom oriented us and gave us more information about their Software. This was very important, so that our programmer could report some of the bugs we found, and then help correct them with the team of development. We have contributed mainly to Mypaint and Blender software.

Free, Open Source software and Free culture are community oriented movements, and shall strive only with a collective investment, it's important to understand the implications of using closed source software, and the power of freedom given by open alternatives.

In conclusion, This project is a solid experience, we will expand it, and finally create a complete videogame. We feel that FOSS has great tools, some need more attention, but with the contribution and feedback from more users, there is room for even more growth.

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